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EFFICIENT IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ENSEMBLE KALMAN FILTER

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Abstract. We present several methods for the efficient implementation of the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) of Evensen. It is shown that the EnKF can be implemented without access to the observation matrix, and only an observation function is needed; this greatly simplifies software design. New implementations of the EnKF formulas are proposed, with linear computational complexity in the number of data points. These implementations are possible when the data covariance matrix is easy to decompose, such as a diagonal or a banded matrix, or given in a factored form as sample covariance. Unlike previous methods, our method for the former case uses Choleski decomposition on a small matrix from the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula instead of SVD on a large matrix, and our method in the latter case does not impose any constraints on data randomization. One version of the EnKF formulas was implemented in a distributed parallel environment, using SCALAPACK and MPI.

1. Introduction. The Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) is a Monte-Carlo implementation of the Bayesian update problem: Given a probability distribution of the modeled system (the prior, called often the forecast in geosciences) and data likelihood, the Bayes theorem is used to obtain the probability distribution with the data likelihood taken into account (the posterior or the analysis). The Bayesian update is combined with advancing the model in time, with the data incorporated from time to time. The original Kalman Filter [14] relies on the assumption that the probability distributions are Gaussian, and provided algebraic formulas for the change of the mean and covariance by the Bayesian update, and a formula for advancing the covariance matrix in time provided the system is linear. However, this is not possible computationally for high dimensional systems. For this reasons, EnKFs were developed [7, 12]. EnKFs represent the distribution of the system state using a random sample, called an ensemble, and replace the covariance matrix by the sample covariance of the ensemble. One advantage of EnKFs is that advancing the probability distribution in time is achieved by simply advancing each member of the ensemble. EnKFs, however, still rely on the Gaussian assumption, though they are of course used in practice for nonlinear problems, where the Gaussian assumption is not satisfied. Related filters attempting to relax the Gaussian assumption in EnKF include [3, 4, 15, 17].

This paper is focused on the Bayesian update step for the EnKF version from [6, 8]. This filter involves randomization of data. For filters without randomization of data, see [2, 9, 16].

The paper is organized as follows. In Sec. 2, we state the Bayesian update formulas in EnKF. In Section 3, we show how to evaluate formulas without an observation matrix, involving observation functions. Sec. 4 contains the discussion of several implementations of the EnKF and their computational complexity. Finally, Sec. 5 briefly reports on the experience from a distributed parallel implementation.

2. Notation and the EnKF Formulas. We review the EnKF formulas following [6, 8], with only one minor difference. The forecast ensemble consists of N members, which are state vectors of dimension n . The ensemble can be written as

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the N by n matrix

$$X^f = [x_1, \dots, x_N] = [x_i]$$

are the forecast ensemble states. The ensemble mean is

$$E(X) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N x_k.$$

and the ensemble covariance matrix is

$$C = \frac{AA^T}{N-1}$$

where

$$A = X - E(X) = X - \frac{1}{N} (X e_{N \times 1}) e_{1 \times N},$$

and e denotes the matrix of all ones of the indicated size.

The data is given as a measurement vector d size m and error covariance matrix R size m by m . Then the measurement matrix D size m by N is defined by

$$D = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N], \quad d_j = d + v_j, \quad v_j \sim N(0, R)$$

where v_j are independent random perturbations.

The analysis ensemble is then given by

$$X^a = X + CH^T (HCH^T + R)^{-1} (D - HX), \quad (2.1)$$

cf., [8, eq. (20)].

The difference between (2.1) and [8, eq. (20)] is that we use the covariance matrix R of the measurement error rather than the sample covariance $DD^T/(N-1)$ of the randomized data. Because R is always positive definite, there is no difficulty with the inverse in (2.1), unlike [8, eq. (20)].

The analysis formula (2.1) can be rewritten similarly as in [8, eq. (54)] as

$$X^a = X + \frac{1}{N-1} A (HA)^T P^{-1} (D - HX) \quad (2.2)$$

where

$$HA = HX - \frac{1}{N} ((HX) e_{N \times 1}) e_{1 \times N}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$P = \frac{1}{N-1} HA (HA)^T + R. \quad (2.4)$$

3. Observation Matrix-Free Method. Clearly, the matrix H in (2.2) – (2.4) is needed only in the matrix vector product HX , which needs to be computed only once. However, it is very inconvenient to operate with the matrix H explicitly for several reasons:

1. An observation function $h(x)$ that creates synthetic data from the state can be quite complicated. Even when the observation function is affine, thus of the form

$$h(x) = Hx + f, \quad (3.1)$$

creating the matrix H and the vector f is an additional effort, which is typically much harder than programming the observation function itself.

2. Computing the matrix-vector product HX takes computational resources.
3. The matrix H is typically sparse and it can be very large. E.g., in the quite common case when every measurement coincides with the value of a state variable, the matrix will have just one one in every row and the rest of its entries are zeros. If the measurement is an image, the number of measurements can be very large, but each pixel in the image is interpolated from just a few entries of the state vector. Assimilation of image data into a geophysical model may easily require $m \approx 10^6$ and $n \approx 10^6$, which makes manipulation of the matrix H stored as full impossible on current computers. So, the matrix H must be stored as sparse, which is an additional complication.

Fortunately, creating the matrix H explicitly is not needed. Assume that we only have access to the evaluation of $h(x)$ in (3.1) but not to the values of H or f . To compute the data residual, note that

$$d - Hx = d + f - (Hx + f) = \tilde{d} - h(x),$$

where

$$\tilde{d} = d + f$$

is the data actually given. To compute HA , note that

$$\begin{aligned} [HA]_i &= Hx_i - H \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \\ &= (Hx_i + f) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (Hx_j + f) \\ &= h(x_i) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N h(x_j). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the ensemble update can be computed by evaluating the observation function h on each ensemble member once.

4. Computational Complexity. All operations in (2.2) – (2.4) are evaluations of the observation function $h(x)$, cf., Sec. 3, and matrix-matrix and matrix-vector operations, which can be implemented efficiently by calls to the LAPACK, BLAS, and SCALAPACK libraries [1, 5]. These libraries contain routines for operations including Choleski decomposition of a symmetric positive definite matrix (CHOL) $LL^T = A$, and matrix multiply (GEMM), $A = \alpha A + \beta B^{(T)}C^{(T)}$, where (T) is either transpose or nothing, for rank update. Recall that m is the number of data points, n is the number degrees of freedom, N is the ensemble size, so X is n by N , HX and HA are m by N , R is m by m . Assume that evaluation of $h(x)$ costs $O(m)$, and that multiplication of matrices of size n_1 by n_2 and n_2 by n_3 costs $O(n_1 n_2 n_3)$.

4.1. Reference Implementation. Straightforward implementation of the formulas (2.2) – (2.4) leads to the following algorithm:

computation	operation	size	cost	}	(4.1)
HX	N times $h(x)$	$m \times N$	$O(mN)$		
$z = (HX) e_{N \times 1}$	matrix multiply	$m \times N \times 1$	$O(mN)$		
$HA = HX - \frac{1}{N} z e_{1 \times N}$	matrix multiply	$m \times 1 \times N$	$O(mN)$		
$Y = D - HX$	matrix add	$m \times N$	$O(mN)$		
$P = R + \frac{1}{N-1} HA (HA)^T$	matrix multiply	$m \times N \times m$	$O(m^2 N)$		
$LL^T = P$	Choleski	m	$O(m^3)$		
$M = P^{-1} Y$	solution	$m \times m \times N$	$O(m^2 N)$		
$Z = (HA)^T M$	matrix multiply	$N \times m \times N$	$O(mN^2)$		
$X^a = X + \frac{1}{N-1} AZ$	matrix multiply	$n \times N \times N$	$O(nN^2)$		

The total computational complexity of the algorithm (4.1) is

$$O(m^3 + m^2 N + mN^2 + nN^2).$$

So, this method is suitable for a large number of degrees of freedom n , but not for a large number of observations m .

4.2. Large Number of Data Points. In practice, the number of data points m is often large, while the data error covariance matrix R is often diagonal (when the data errors are uncorrelated), nearly diagonal, or easy to decompose. This happens, e.g., in the assimilation of images, or in regularized EnKF where the gradient of fields in the state is assimilated as an additional artificial observation [13]. In this case, the following algorithm, which has only linear complexity in m , provides a significant advantage. Assume that multiplication by R^{-1} is dominated by other costs. Using the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula [11]

$$(R + UV^T)^{-1} = R^{-1} - R^{-1}U(I + V^T R^{-1}U)^{-1}V^T R^{-1},$$

with

$$U = \frac{1}{N-1} HA, \quad V = HA,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} P^{-1} &= \left(R + \frac{1}{N-1} HA (HA)^T \right)^{-1} \\ &= R^{-1} \left[I - \frac{1}{N-1} (HA) \left(I + (HA)^T R^{-1} \frac{1}{N-1} (HA) \right)^{-1} (HA)^T R^{-1} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

The computation (4.1) then becomes

computation	operation	size	cost
HX	N times $h(x)$	$m \times N$	$O(mN)$
$z = (HX) e_{N \times 1}$	matrix multiply	$m \times N \times 1$	$O(mN)$
$HA = HX - \frac{1}{N} z e_{1 \times N}$	matrix multiply	$m \times 1 \times N$	$O(mN)$
$Y = D - HX$	matrix add	$m \times N$	$O(mN)$
$Q = I + (HA)^T R^{-1} \frac{1}{N-1} (HA)$	matrix multiply	$N \times m \times M$	$O(mN^2)$
$LL^T = Q$	Choleski	N	$O(N^3)$
$Z = (HA)^T R^{-1} Y$	matrix multiply	$N \times m \times N$	$O(mN^2)$
$W = Q^{-1} Z$	solution	$N \times N$	$O(N^3)$
$M = R^{-1} \left[I - \frac{1}{N-1} (HA) W \right]$	matrix multiply	$m \times N \times N$	$O(mN^2)$
$Z = (HA)^T M$	matrix multiply	$N \times m \times N$	$O(mN^2)$
$X^a = X + \frac{1}{N-1} AZ$	matrix multiply	$n \times N \times N$	$O(nN^2)$

(4.2)

This gives overall complexity $O(N^3 + mN^2 + nN^2)$, which is suitable for large n and large m .

4.3. Square Root Alternative. Decompose first $R = SS^T$, e.g., by Choleski decomposition, and multiplication by S^{-1} is cheap to compute. Let $\tilde{U} = S^{-1}U$, $\tilde{V} = S^{-1}V$. Then the Sherman-Morrison-Woodbury formula becomes

$$(SS^T + UV^T)^{-1} = S^{-T} \left[I - \tilde{U} \left(I + \tilde{V}^T \tilde{U} \right)^{-1} \tilde{V} \right] S^{-1},$$

which gives, again with $R = SS^T$, $B = S^{-1}HA$

$$P^{-1} = S^{-T} \left[I - \frac{1}{N-1} B \left(I + \frac{1}{N-1} B^T B \right)^{-1} B^T \right] S^{-1}$$

and one proceeds just as in Sec. 4.2. The asymptotic complexity is same as in Sec. 4.2, but the formulas involve symmetric products of matrices, which is numerically more stable and allows to save memory by storing just one triangle.

4.4. SVD Method for Full Data Error Covariance. Assume again that $R = SS^T$ and multiplication by S^{-1} is cheap to compute. Write

$$P = \frac{1}{N-1} HA (HA)^T + R = S \left[\frac{1}{N-1} S^{-1} HA (HA)^T S^{-T} + I \right] S^T$$

and use the singular value decomposition (SVD) [10]

$$S^{-1} HA = U \Sigma V^T,$$

where U and V are orthogonal square matrices, and $\Sigma = \text{diag}_{m \times N}(\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_k)$ is the diagonal matrix size m by N with the singular values $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_k$, $k = \min\{m, N\}$, on the diagonal; then, using the orthogonality relations $V^T V = I$, $U U^T = I$, we have

$$\frac{1}{N-1} S^{-1} HA (HA)^T S^{-T} + I = \frac{1}{N-1} U \Sigma U^T + I = U \left(\frac{\Sigma^2}{N-1} + I \right) U^T$$

thus

$$P^{-1} = R^{-1/2}U^T \operatorname{diag} \left(\frac{1}{\frac{\sigma_i^2}{N+1} + 1} \right) UR^{-1/2}$$

The complexity is again $O(mN^2)$, assuming that $m > N$ and that computation of SVD of matrix size m by N costs $O(mN \min(m, N))$.

4.5. SVD and Eigenvalue Methods for Sample Data Error Covariance.

It should be noted that the use of SVD in Sec. 4.4 is different than in [8], where spectral methods and SVD were advocated as a device to overcome the singularity of the data sample covariance matrix R , given as $R = SS^T / (N - 1)$ with S size $m \times N$. In that case, [8, eq. (56)] suggests the eigenvalue decomposition for the matrix

$$P = \frac{1}{N-1} \left(HA(HA)^T + SS^T \right) = Z\Lambda Z^T, \quad (4.3)$$

which is size m by m but there are only N nonzero eigenvalues, i.e., diagonal entries of Λ . If the matrix P is created explicitly, the cost of the decomposition (4.3) is between $O(m^2N)$ and $O(m^3)$.

However, we note that in this case, P can be written as

$$P = \frac{1}{N-1} FF^T, \quad F = [HA, S], \quad (4.4)$$

where F has size m by $2N$. Therefore, applying the SVD decomposition to the matrix W , we obtain $W = U\Sigma V^T$, and

$$P^{-1} = (N-1)U\Sigma^{-2}U^T. \quad (4.5)$$

The matrix U is size m by m but it has only $2N$ nonzero columns, and SVD routines actually return the m by $2N$ submatrix, at the cost $O(mN^2)$. The resulting algorithm, using the multiplication by factored P^{-1} from (4.5) in (2.1), has again the cost $O(N^3 + mN^2 + nN^2)$. [8, eq. (57)] discusses a method using SVD, with the same asymptotic cost, but requiring the data perturbation selected in a special way. No such constraint is needed here.

4.6. Iterative Methods. The linear system $PM = Y$ can be solved by conjugate gradients for N right-hand sides. However, each iteration costs $O(mN^2)$, so iterative methods do not seem to be competitive.

5. Distributed Parallel Implementation. The method described in Sec. 4.2 was implemented in a distributed parallel environment using MPI and SCALAPACK. EnKF is naturally parallel: each ensemble member can be advanced in time independently. The linear algebra in the Bayesian update step links the ensemble members together. The ensemble matrix X is then naturally distributed so that each process owns a block of columns. However, such distribution is a bottleneck to parallelism: SCALAPACK requires that all matrices involved in an operation must be distributed on the same processor grid (though possibly with different block sizes), and, for best performance, the processor grid should be close to a square. 1D processor grids tend to be particularly inefficient. Therefore, the ensemble matrix must be redistributed before the matrix linear algebra operations.

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